

Uses & Gratification of mobile apps for information sharing in higher education of Haryana

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Abstract

Mobile applications, popularly known as mobile apps, are increasing day by day at a very high speed. Especially youth from universities today use smartphones for information as well as entertainment. The study focuses on how frequently information is being shared using mobile apps, which are the preferred mobile applications for receiving and forwarding images, photographs, audio, and video content, sharing links, downloading, sharing in groups, and how much these apps help in studies for university students. Researchers did descriptive research to meet the objectives, followed by a cross-sectional research design. We conducted a survey among the three main university students in the Haryana state of India with purposive sampling. The study shows that university students are also using mobile apps to share information with friends, family, and relatives. For this purpose, WhatsApp is the most preferred mobile app, and they use WhatsApp to download, forward, receive, and send photographs, audio, and video clips to individuals and groups as well. Sometimes they share YouTube video links. Students also have mixed responses to downloading videos received from mobile messaging apps, and these apps are also contributing a lot to their studies. Overall, the use of mobile apps is incredible for sharing information among university students in Haryana. Students feel mobile apps positively contribute to their studies. Female students consider WhatsApp more helpful in their studies than male students.

Keywords: WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook Messenger, YouTube, Google Duo and youth of Haryana

1.0 Introduction:

Mobile applications, alias mobile apps, are something we see everywhere around us in our day-to-day lives. It has changed the trends of markets, hospitals, entertainment, education, social interactions, event planning, and everything else into mobile apps. Mobile apps have broadened everyone's perspective. According to Steckman & Andrews, social media has become an integral part of people's lives. Digital media provides real-time and rapid communication, including content sharing among people all over the globe (Steckman & Andrews, 2017).

Talking about any new start-ups, the generation belonging to the 21st century brings out new ideas, but most of these ideas extensively revolve around mobile applications and websites. Today's youth especially depend on apps like WhatsApp, Facebook, etc. (Kumar & Sharma, 2023). They getting every happening through these apps quickly, even if they miss certain things in mainstream media. Apps such as Google Meet, Zoom, and Microsoft Team are being used to conduct online classes for long-distance learners. Mobile apps are preferably used for everything, whether it is for sharing information, entertainment, studying, or anything else. According to Hill and Bradshaw, having a large number of users who like your content on Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter is always desirable (Hill & Bradshaw, 2019).

Today, it is common practice among university, college, and school students to share notes, videos, pictures, links, and study material via mobile applications. Sharing information is very convenient with the help of these apps (Sharma & Kumar, 2023). Teachers can easily post notes and any other multimedia material over these apps, where students can go anytime as per their comfort. Undoubtedly, things for students and teachers have become easier with these new developments. Mobile apps have embraced classroom teaching, which enhances learning or perhaps provides better interference. Smartphones have also changed the face of classroom teaching (Anshari et al., 2017).

1.1 Mobile applications

In terms of its fundamental nature, a mobile application (or "mobile app") can be defined as a software or computer program. It is designed to function on mobile devices such as smartphones, tablets, and similar gadgets. Although new technology has given

an extension to mobile applications which run on desktop or laptop, so it can also be called a desktop version of mobile applications. WhatsApp and Twitter (now X) are also available on desktop versions.

Initially, apps were initiated for productivity assistance like email, contact details database and such other things. But with the rapid use of mobile applications, now apps for communication, banking, games, education and shopping are also available on Google play store, Microsoft Store and over many other platforms. People can book railway, bus, and plane tickets with the help of mobile applications. People can fill electricity bills, pay tax, recharge their mobile or dish TV and can do many more tasks with the help of mobile applications. If people talk about the popularity of these mobile apps, the term mobile application becomes more popular in the year 2010 (*“App” Voted 2010 Word of the Year by the American Dialect Society (UPDATED), 2011*).

Now mobile apps are highly demanded by mobile users. After observing the market, most mobile tech companies are selling mobile devices with some pre-installed applications or software. Now web browsers, email applications, media apps, music apps, games, apps of Google like YouTube and many more are already installed in the mobile sets. Users can easily install mobile apps as per their demand. These applications can be downloaded or updated from time to time from the device's mobile operating system like Apps Store (iOS), Google Play Store, MI Store, Galaxy Store and Amazon Appstore and many more. Mobile applications can be downloaded from various platforms but sometimes users can download these applications from a laptop or desktop. It can be installed manually with some easy steps followed by the users. Some mobile applications are freeware it means these are available free of cost while some other are paid which means users have to pay to run these types of applications. Some apps earn money through advertisements and many other mediums. The earnings are usually divided between mobile apps creators and app store owners (Siegler, 2008). As per their technical classification mobile apps can be categorised into native, web-based and hybrid apps. Native apps are made for a particular mobile platform like Android and Apple. These apps are intended for Apple or Android devices and do not run on other devices. The motto behind creating these apps is to make sure best

performance on the specific mobile operating system like Apple or Android. While a web-based app is executed with web technologies of JavaScript, CSS or HTML. To run these applications, proper internet access is needed. Most of these apps stored data in the cloud. On the other hand, the hybrid apps have mixed features of native and web-based apps. As far as the technology is concerned, apps developed by using Apache Cordova, Sencha Touch, React Native and Xamarin falls into the hybrid apps category. Hybrid apps are produced to assist both web and native technologies across multiple operating platforms (Sharma et al., 2022).

1.2 Communication apps

Mobile communication apps are very common in India. Most of the mobile users are using apps for communication and instant messaging purpose. The report of Steup, M. (2018) published on messenger people.com stated that communication applications are very commonly used in the digital era of communication. Mobile users use WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Viber, Twitter, JioCall, Skype, IMO, Telegram and other apps for communication and educational purposes. These communication apps are used globally for communication purposes, which is another reason for the popularity of these apps. More than 560 million mobile users are using the internet as per the report published in 2019, while 89% of these users are using mobile messaging apps like WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger and Viber etc. This report indicates that Facebook Messenger was the most downloaded app in the year 2018 while WhatsApp is most popular in the terms of active users. This report indicates that WhatsApp is installed in about 95% of Android and Apple technology based mobile phones and out of the 75% are using this app on a daily basis (Potor, 2023).

As per the latest report of Similar Web (2021) for top apps ranking, WhatsApp is the most popular communication apps followed by Facebook Messenger which is highly used by Indian citizens. Telegram is 3rd most popular mobile communication app in India followed by Google Duo which is also used by the countrymen. Indian Mobile Phone users are using Imo free calls and chat. JioCall, Signal Private Messenger, Hangouts, Skype, CallApp, Viber and other more than 40 applications to fulfil communication and information need (*Top Apps Ranking*, 2021).

1.3. Importance of the study:

It is always important to learn about new media technology and its use in communication and education. Social media is widely-used communication platform among all age groups but it is very popular among the youth. Social media have given wings to the modern teaching and learning process. People learn day and night via this technological advanced platform. The beauty of the media platform is that this is user-driven, and a lot of user-generated content is available here, if any technology gives many benefits, then it could be harmful too. The same concept is applied in the case of social media platforms. Many scholars suggested that social media is a good platform for interaction-communication and social learning but its overuse is harmful to students as well as others (Sharma & Goyal, 2018). It badly affects academic performance and negatively affects the health of users. The importance of the study is as follows.

1. This study is very helpful to know about the frequency of receiving & sending information via mobile apps among university students.
2. This study is an attempt to analyse the utilisation of mobile apps for sharing information among youth.
3. Researchers had tried to explore the interest, regarding participation in groups by students which tells the social learning habits and process of the students.
4. This study is also helpful to understand the accessibility of mobile apps for studies and sharing information among youth.

2.0 Review of literature

This part of the study contains reviews of the available research work on the related topic. In a research article Santoso (2021) tried to find out the use of social media and online news to make people aware of political issues. Data is collected from social media and online news by using web crawlers and the SNA method. The result indicates that online news and social media is playing a valuable role in spreading information regarding nationalism. Political professionals and political elites use social media and online news to spread awareness about nationalism (Santoso, 2021).

In their research work, Aminah & Saksono (2021) analyzed the development of digital innovation and old technology was replaced by new technology. Researchers did qualitative research to meet the objectives. They collected secondary data for the research purpose. The result indicates that ICT development and digital service for community need is growing very fast. Digital transformation is the need of the hour, it should be done with effective collaboration of the government and institutions (Aminah & Saksono, 2021).

In their research work, Kumar, Sharma, & Verma (2021) explained social media as a tool for social and political inclusion among youth. Social media is a good tool for sharing information and spreading awareness. The researchers surveyed the quantitative research approach. The result indicates that social media apps are assisting students in a big way. They easily make communication with friends, family members and colleagues for official and unofficial communication. Overuse of social media creates negative effects on youth. Youth think that political parties are using social media as a tool of propaganda (S. Kumar et al., 2021).

In a study Thang et al. (2020) analyzed the awareness level regarding the risks and dangers of social networking among school level students. The researchers conducted the survey using a quantitative research approach. They collected questionnaires from the respondents i.e. school going students. Results indicate that all students are aware of the risks and dangers coupled with social networking. But elite school's students and girls are more aware than others. A big number of students lack awareness regarding privacy issues. Most students are unable to protect themselves online (Thang et al., 2020).

In their research work, Syam & Nurrahmi (2020) analyzed the social media literacy of Indonesian university students. With the growth and access of the internet, social media is growing very speedily. This speedy growth is due to easy and anytime access to social media. Researchers used mixed methods i.e. quantitative and qualitative. For quantitative research, researchers used the survey method and collected 500 questionnaires from the respondents. For qualitative research, researchers have done Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The result indicates that university students are less aware of media literacy and about fake news. Sometimes they face some difficulty to discern between fake news and real news. Researchers suggested a new model for media literacy that helps identify fake news (Syam & Nurrahmi, 2020).

Rashid, Aziz, Rahman, Saaid & Ahmad (2020) tried to find out the influence of mobile phone addiction on academic performance among teenagers. Media and communication techniques have changed teenager's routine life. Internet and mobile phones are very popular communication revolutions in the recent era. The researchers opted for descriptive research and survey methods to meet the objective. 200 Questionnaire has been collected from the school students aged 13 to 17 years old. The result indicates that mobile phones are very useful for communication and connectivity among school students. Although, unrestricted use of mobile phones negatively affects the academic score of the students. It is recommended that overuse of mobile phone for communication and interaction is lead to mobile addiction which has certain negative effects (Abd. Rashid et al., 2020).

In research work, Kumar and Nanda (2019) evaluated the process of learning via mobile phone. They find out that mobile is a very important tool for gaining information. With the assistance of mobile applications, distance and online learning can be executed with remarkable ease. Scholars have proposed that mobile technology integration and the development of a learning-theoretical framework to direct policy planning, practice, and learning must be strengthened (Kumar & Nanda, 2019).

In a study, Sharma & Goyal (2018) analyzed Twitter as a tool for political communication. Researchers applied the content analysis method to know how BJP's Official Twitter Handle is spreading information in society. As per the result is a concern, BJP's official Twitter handle is used to spread micro or positive agenda and no propaganda. Information is shared on media platforms in a very neutral and positive way (Sharma & Goyal, 2018).

3.0 Research method:

This segment of the research paper comprises the research inquiries, research goals, research methodology, and sample structure.

3.1 Research questions:

Q1. What is the frequency of receiving & sending information via mobile apps among university students in Haryana?

Q2. What is the utilization of mobile apps for sharing information?

Q3. How many students are interested in participating in the group?

Q4. How effective are mobile applications for information exchange and education among young people?

3.2 Objectives:

- To know about the frequency of receiving & sending information via mobile apps among university students in Haryana.
- To analyse the utilisation of mobile apps for sharing information.
- To explore the interest regarding participation in groups by students.
- To access the effectiveness of mobile apps for studies and sharing information for youth.

3.3 Research design:

The present study is descriptive. The survey method has opted for the research. A Survey is conducted over 100 students of Haryana's two universities namely Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra and Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak. The largest university in the Indian state of Haryana is both extremely ancient. A survey was conducted in accordance with a cross-sectional research design. In order to achieve the aims, a closed-ended questionnaire was employed. Use and Gratification theory inform the research.

3.4 Sample design:

For purposes of this research, the universe consists of every university student. University students from across the nation are regarded as the study's sampling population. University students in Haryana comprise the sampling unit for this study. Utilizing a stratified random sampling technique, the responses of the respondents, who are university students from Haryana, were gathered. Two most old and reputed universities namely Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra and MD University, Rohtak has been chosen for the study. Sampling is done through stratification of 50 students each from the Undergraduate (UG) and Post Graduate (PG) levels. Equal distribution was done in male and female respondents for collecting their opinion, it covers 25 male and 25

female students each from UG and PG levels. Samples are collected during the academic session 2018-2019. Researchers had applied the Cochran formula for sample size calculation with a 90% confidence level, 2000 population, 8% margin of error. After applying an online sample size calculator, researchers got an ideal sample size=101. Researchers have collected responses in hard copies of questionnaires. The questionnaire was formulated with questions related to the usage of mobile internet, mobile applications and its utilization in day to day life for communication. Further data is analyzed with cross-tabulation according to male and female distribution with percentage.

3.5 Research tool and technique:

For the present study, researchers used Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version-20.0 for data analysis and representation. Along with this, they used MS Office for data representation in a proper manner. Data is showed in both frequency and percentage form so that common people can easily understand the data. Data are presented in tables.

4.0 Data analysis and presentation

In the contemporary world, mobile phones are the most valuable instrument. This portable technology is essential for all demographics, including children, adults, women, students, and even the young. Carrying a mobile device is comparable to carrying the entire universe with you. We are capable of conversing, chatting, reading, downloading, sharing, connecting socially, entertaining, and informing one another. This study is based on an analysis of information sharing trends among university students. For this purpose, a survey was conducted among 100 students from UG and PG level Universities in Haryana. A questionnaire was formulated with questions related to the usage of mobile applications and their utilization in day to day life for Information sharing among peer groups and usefulness for their studies.

4.1 Preferred App for sharing photographs/pictures/images

Today various mobile apps provide a platform for sharing a large variety of data including audio, video, photographs, documents, links, etc. Photographs/Pictures/images are sometimes a very important source of information. Table-1 represents the preferred mobile application for sharing or sending images to others individually or a group of people in just a single command. WhatsApp

is dominantly preferred, as about 60 percent of students use it for sharing images among their peer group. 68 percent of female students use WhatsApp for sending pictures to their friends, family and other relatives whereas 58 percent of Male students use WhatsApp, but they also give some preference to Instagram with 34 percent. Overall Instagram today has become second preference among youth for sending photographs to youth with 28 percent. Facebook Messenger is used by merely 9 percent of students whereas only 6 percent of female students use other mobile apps for this purpose. Today students share a variety of images with these apps from morning greetings tonight greetings, notes, jokes, schedules, posters, pamphlets, screenshots, photographs, illustrations, etc.

Table-1: Preferred Apps for sharing Photographs/Pictures/Images by Students gender wise

Gender	WhatsApp	Instagram	Facebook Messenger	Others	Total (%)
Male	26 (52.0)	17 (34.0)	7 (14.0)	0	50 (100)
Female	34 (68.0)	11 (22.0)	2 (4.0)	3 (6.0)	50 (100)
Total (%)	60	28	9	3	100

4.2 Preferred App for Sharing Audio & Video Content

Today internet provides great source of audio and video content from wide-ranging categories. Various mobile apps support sharing of this type of content to others. Table-2 indicates that the trends of sharing audio-video clippings with different messaging applications. About 89 percent of students share audio-video content using WhatsApp only and most of the females use this media more frequently. The remaining 11 (2+6+3) percent of students utilize other apps for sharing audio and video files. Few Male respondents use Facebook Messenger (12%) and Instagram (4%) for sharing such content whereas female students do not prefer these two platforms and opt for other apps. So, WhatsApp is most preferred among youth for sharing

audio-video content to friends, family and relatives this includes songs, jokes, motivational content, funny videos, informational videos, advertisements, news reports, educational content etc.

Table-2: Preferred Apps for Sharing Audio & Video Content by Students gender wise

Gender	WhatsApp	Instagram	Facebook Messenger	Others	Total (%)
Male	42 (84.0)	2 (4.0)	6 (12.0)	0	50 (100)
Female	47 (94.0)	0	0	3 (6.0)	50 (100)
Total (%)	89	2	6	3	100

4. 3 Sharing of YouTube links

With the enormous growth in the internet infrastructure, it is providing an online video streaming platform. YouTube is now providing billions of videos of different genres from armature to highly professionals. YouTube provide the opportunity to share the video links to share with other prospective users. Table-3 indicates that about one-third of the students sometimes share YouTube video links to others whereas about one-fourth share such links.19 percent of students always prefer to share such links to others to watch videos on this platform whereas only eight percent of total students were often interested in sharing links via mobile apps.14 percent of youth are never find sharing links are fruitful for others. More male students always desire to share than females but more females consider sometimes than male students. YouTube provide a variety of video channels to the various kind of target audience.

Table-3: Sharing of YouTube Links by Students gender wise

Gender	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Total (%)
Male	14 (28.0)	4 (8.0)	15 (30.0)	12 (24.0)	5 (10.0)	50 (100)
Female	5 (10.0)	4 (8.0)	18 (36.0)	14 (28.0)	9 (18.0)	50 (100)

Total (%)	19	8	33	26	14	100
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4.4 Number of images downloaded & forwarded via mobile apps

From morning to night, most mobile users are receiving and sending different kinds of images to their contacts. Mobile apps give the option to download and forward these images to other known persons. The frequency of downloading and forwarding these images helps in knowing how well these apps are used by students for sharing information. About 70 percent of the students send and receive less than 10 images in a day whereas 23 percent of respondents download and forward images between 10 to 20 as indicated in Table-4. Few students are sharing images between 21 to 30 and above 40 images in a single day. Male and female respondent has a mere difference in their frequency of downloading and forwarding of images. It can be considered that little use, normal use, extra use and overuse. Here we find that this feature of downloading and forwarding images via mobile apps have little too normal utilization among university students.

Table-4: Number of Images Downloaded & Forwarded with these Apps by Students gender wise

Gender	Less than 10	10 to 20	21 to 30	More than 40	Total (%)
Male	34 (68.0)	12 (24.0)	2 (4.0)	2 (4.0)	50 (100)
Female	36 (72.0)	11 (22.0)	2 (4.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100)
Total (%)	70	23	4	3	100

4.5 Preference for Downloading Videos from Mobile Messaging Apps

Various mobile messaging apps provide the facility to send and receive audio and video files from their peer group, family members and relations. One-third of the students sometimes download videos shared via mobile apps. 10 percent of male and female students never download videos from mobile messaging apps as indicated in Table-5 whereas 15 percent of students always download

videos and this category is dominating by female students. About 28 percent rarely prefer to download whereas only 14 percent of students often download videos with this service. Most of the students fall in sometimes to never group for downloading video clips shared via mobile apps.

Table-5: Preference for Downloading Videos from Mobile Messaging Apps by Students gender wise

Gender	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Total (%)
Male	6 (12.0)	5 (10.0)	21 (42.0)	13 (26.0)	5 (10.0)	50 (100)
Female	9 (18.0)	9 (18.0)	12 (24.0)	15 (30.0)	5 (10.0)	50 (100)
Total (%)	15	14	33	28	10	100

4. 6 Participation in Groups with mobile Apps

Today, mobile messaging apps like Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, Instagram and others provide add-on facilities to make a group of friends, family and relatives and some special groups etc. This facility helps in sharing instant information from any member to all other members of the group with a single command. About 38 percent of university students find sometimes participating in such groups as per Table-6 whereas only 10 percent of students never participate in these groups and they prefer to communicate individually. This feature is always and often used more by female than male students. About one-fourth of the students rarely use groups for sharing Information. Group participation allows sharing messages, images, audio videos, links, documents etc. instantly to students in a group for better communication.

Table-6: Participation in Groups with these Apps by Students gender wise

Gender	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Total (%)
Male	3 (6.0)	7 (14.0)	20 (40.0)	15 (30.0)	5 (10.0)	50 (100)

Female	8 (16.0)	8 (16.0)	18 (36.0)	11 (22.0)	5 (10.0)	50 (100)
Total (%)	11	15	38	26	10	100

4. 7 Apps Helping in Studies

Sharing information is helpful to keep updating about various related content. Specifically, students are getting valuable information related to their studies from school, coaching institutions, friends, and teachers etc. About one third each finds these mobile apps as much and normally helpful in their studies as indicated in Table-7. About half of the females find it as much helpful whereas about 40 percent of male students find it normal. Out of 100 respondents, 2 male respondents have not responded about the use of mobile apps for studies. 13 percent and 5 percent of students find it little and not at all helpful in studies respectively. Most of the student's viz 80.7 percent (i.e. 15.3+32.7+32.7) find mobile apps are helpful for their studies in very much to normal category and among female students, they find it more helpful than male respondents.

Table-7: Apps Helpful in Studies by Students gender wise

Gender	Very Much	Much	Normal	Little	Not at all	Total(%)
Male	7 (14.6)	9 (18.8)	19 (39.6)	9 (18.8)	4 (8.3)	48 (100)
Female	8 (16.0)	23 (46.0)	14 (28.0)	4 (8.0)	1 (2.0)	50 (100)
Total (%)	15 (15.3)	32 (32.7)	33 (33.7)	13 (13.0)	5 (5.1)	98 (100)

Note: Two male respondents not responded.

4.8: Rating of Receiving and Sending Message with mobile Apps

It is important to know overall experience about the use of mobile apps for sharing Information among youth. These apps have provided a platform for sending and receiving messages instantly with acknowledgement of receiving the message. About half of the students find this as a good tool for sharing information in which females are more dominant than males as per Table-8. About one-fourth of the students feel this is a very good platform for sending and receiving information in this males are more ahead of female students.14 percent of males and

females find this as excellent whereas only 14 percent of males find this as an outstanding model of communication. Overall university students surely find these mobile apps are contributing to sharing valuable information.

Table-8: Rating of Receiving and Sending Message with mobile Apps by Students gender wise

Gender	Average	Good	Very good	Excellent	Outstanding	Total (%)
Male	4 (8.0)	18 (36.0)	14 (28.0)	7 (14.0)	7 (14.0)	50 (100)
Female	5 (10.0)	29 (58.0)	9 (18.0)	7 (14.0)	0	50 (100)
Total (%)	9	47	23	14	7	100

5.0 Result:

The major result regarding trends of mobile applications for communication among university students are as follows:

- ✓ WhatsApp is the most preferred mobile app among 60 percent of university students for sharing images/ pictures/ photographs with friends, family and relatives. Instagram is also taking place for such provision as liked by 28 percent of respondents.
- ✓ 89 percent of students find WhatsApp as the most suitable app for sharing audio and video content by students. Female students find WhatsApp more helpful than male students.
- ✓ Sharing YouTube links using mobile apps find mixed responses among youth. One-third sometimes feel this to be shared with others.
- ✓ About 70 percent of students prefer to download and forward less than 10 images in a day while about one-fourth of students share 10 to 20 images in a day means moderate use of this feature.
- ✓ Students have mixed reactions regarding the preference of downloading videos via mobile messaging apps.

- ✓ More than one-third of students sometimes participate in a group whereas many students rarely and some students never presume benefit out of participating in such groups via mobile apps.
- ✓ Most of the students feel these mobile apps positively contribute to their studies. Female students consider WhatsApp more helpful in studies than males.
- ✓ Most of the students rate these mobile apps from average to very good for sharing information whereas 14 percent of male respondents each find it as an excellent and outstanding tool.

6.0 Conclusion

Sharing information via mobile phone apps is playing a decisive role in daily life. Students are also using mobile apps for sharing and connecting virtually with friends, family and relatives. WhatsApp is the most preferred app among university students for sharing, downloading and forwarding photographs, pictures, images, audio and video content. YouTube links for various video files find mixed responses among youth. Most of the students download and forward little to the normal number of images to others. Downloading video from these apps also has a mixed choice for downloading. Students find these apps are significantly helpful in their studies. Participating in group communication among students on these apps does not find much importance. Overall student rates these mobile apps are tremendous and find them helpful for sharing information. Mobile messaging apps are contributing extensively to the pace of communication and helping in every aspect of human's life.

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